

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

SOCIAL USEFUL PURPOSES OF NON-PROFIT ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

This article analyzes the useful goals of non-profit organizations for the benefit of society based on foreign experiences. The goals of strengthening the legal status of non-profit organizations, their independent activities and organization of donations are also studied. In common law countries, there are less "hybrid" forms of non-profit organizations, since charities in these countries can always carry out almost all business activities. At the same time, the socially useful goals of the organization (regardless of the form) are considered as non-profit organizations, since their main function is officially declared as "service to society".

Keywords: non-profit organization, hybrid, socially useful, service to society, public interest, independent activity, civil associations

INTRODUCTION

A distinctive feature of the regulation of the activities of non-profit organizations in the legislation of countries where common law applies is the initial possibility of using a corporation, a limited liability company to obtain the status of a non-profit organization. Sometimes this form is filled with a certain legal feature. At common law, the purposes of private organizations are not primarily a matter of legislative regulation; the presumption that it was established to carry out legitimate purposes applies. At the same time, restrictions were placed on trade organizations and legal practices requiring special permits. In relation to non-profit organizations in common law countries, there are fewer 'hybrid' forms than on the continent (indeed their activities may be 'hybrid'), as charities in these countries (from the UK onwards) are each could always carry out almost all business activities. At the same time, since the main function of companies is officially declared as "service to society", the socially useful goals of the organization (regardless of the form) are considered as non-profit organizations, since they are not "self-financing". Mandatory (although not always effective) follow-up control in connection with the company's compliance with the objectives, first of all, many of them have tax benefits. Thus, the activities of any organization are divided into taxable and non-taxable types.

In common law countries, the term "Non-Governmental Organizations" is rarely used in the academic literature, as state-sponsored organizations and government agencies traditionally fit the definition of NGOs. In this regard, all NGOs are usually called "non-profit" (non-profit - not for profit), and can also have the status of "public benefit" and "charity" organizations.

Currently, in common law countries, the organizational forms of non-profit (especially charitable) activities are regulated by law, although there is a lot of judicial precedent in this area. Therefore, the "independent" and "non-profit" status of the organization must be confirmed in the courts.

The activities of non-governmental non-profit organizations in Bulgaria are regulated by the Law "On

Non-profit Legal Entities" adopted in 2001. This law regulates the composition of government structures and the procedure for the activities of non-governmental organizations (voting procedure, quorum, etc.). However, in addition to court registration, there are organizations that can be registered as public organizations by the Ministry of Justice (with privileges).

The legal status of associations in Turkey is based on Article 5253 of November 4, 2004 [1] and Article 72 of the 2001 Civil Code [2], associations are established by three main governing bodies: the general board, the executive body, and the audit commission (supervisory board). The Law on Unions also defines the powers of these bodies. The association acquires the status of a legal entity after submitting the charter and other documents to the city government. According to the law, in accordance with Article 62 of the Civil Code, the Association must convene its first meeting and organize internal management bodies within 60 days from the moment the charter is sent to the registration body. Article 74 of the Civil Code and Law and Article 9 of the Law "On Associations" govern internal management. Meetings should be held at least once every three years. The head of the association is authorized to check the activity of the association in order to achieve the goals established by law. He also checks the procedure of keeping accounts, presents the control results to the executive body and the general meeting for consideration. According to Article 23 of the law, newly elected members of the executive and control bodies are required to submit reports to the governor within 30 days after the general meeting.

In Poland, non-governmental organizations are usually created in the form of associations and foundations. According to the Law on Associations of 1989, an association must be registered in the place of incorporation (Article 8). After that, information about the Association is entered into the State Court Register. Each association must establish at least three leading bodies: the general council, the governing body and the internal control body. The order of their creation, composition and powers are regulated by the statute. Com-

pliance with the law will be checked at the time of registration with the local court. In May 2016, the Law "On Association" was amended (Articles 40-42), according to which a new type of association was introduced - "simplified"[3]. Such an association does not have the status of a legal entity (paragraph 1 of Article 40), cannot establish local branches, cannot join the union of associations, have legal entities as founders or participants, carry out economic activities, make any contribution or charity. may accept donations and have participant contributions (Article 42). Article 22 of the Law allows the formation of associations of associations, which form at least three associations. Other legal entities may also be part of the founders.

Article 3 of the 1984 Law on Foundations [3] provides that a foundation can be established on the basis of a notarial document expressing the will of the founder. The law does not specify a minimum or maximum payment. If the company plans to carry out business activities, the Fund must have at least 1000 Polish zlotys*. The fund may engage in business activities to achieve its goals (Article 5, Clause 5). It is noted that the existence of authorized capital in each fund is considered the only mandatory body of the organization - management body. There are no other special requirements in the legislation.

In Sweden, "non-governmental organizations" are non-profit or non-profit community-based organizations. A general approach to them is that no registration is required. If an NGO does not carry out any commercial operations, it must be registered with the Swedish Patent and Registration Office under the 1974 Trademarks Registration Act. In order to register a non-governmental organization as a legal entity, the minimum requirements must be met: the NGO must have a founding document and an executive committee. Finland, unlike Sweden, has Association Act 503/1989 [4]. In its articles 7 and 8, the basic rules and internal rules developed during the formation of the association, the minimum and maximum number of members of the executive committee and auditors, their term of office, the reporting year, the conditions for choosing the annual committee and auditors, as well as the general the date of the meeting is indicated. Association registration is carried out by the National Patent and Registration Office. The application for registration of the association shall be submitted in writing together with the charter and internal rules. The state registration body verifies the correctness of the information and its name and other characteristics. Associations may be given time if there are problems with registration. All changes made to the constituent documents, as well as the authorization to sign on behalf of the association, must be registered. The law regulates the voting procedure at the general meeting of the association, including possible special forms (by mail, etc.). If the meeting is not held in a regular manner, each of the members of the association has the right to demand its convening. Emergency meetings can be held.

The main law on non-governmental non-profit organizations in Latvia is the Law on Associations and Foundations of 2003.[5] (The 1992 Act applies in part). Article 12 of the Law applies to associations and private foundations. The law does not apply to political parties, religious organizations, trade and trade unions, and

public foundations, as each type of such organization is regulated by special laws. The law adopted in 2003 contains a set of rules regulating the internal structure of non-governmental non-commercial organizations. At least two people are required to establish an organization. When the association is established, the legislation requires only two governing bodies: 1) general meeting of participants; 2) an executive body consisting of one or more members. Unlike the 1992 Act, there is no requirement to appoint a permanent auditor or an audit committee - their duties can be carried out by the executive. In addition, a non-governmental non-commercial organization has the right to establish other management bodies or determine the internal structure at its discretion according to the main contract. Charter non-profit organizations, as well as the changes introduced, must be transferred to the register of non-governmental non-profit organizations, and the organization must be registered in the national registry in order to acquire legal capacity. If the registration body does not comply with the requirements of the law, the registration period will be extended and a time will be set for making changes to the charter. If changes are not made, the registration body will make a decision to refuse registration. The decision of the registering body can be appealed to the administrative court in the general administrative procedure.

In federal countries (USA, Canada, Australia), the status of joint ventures is usually regulated at the level of federal entities, but "preferential treatment" is given at the federal level. There is no specific law governing NGOs in England and Wales. According to Article 1 of the Charity Law adopted in 2006, they are organizations established "solely for charitable purposes". Article 2 states that charity "serves the public interest" which includes, inter alia, preventing and combating the spread of poverty, promoting education, spreading religion, protecting human rights, and protecting and improving the environment. In this way, "charitable purpose" can be interpreted very broadly. 1-44 Charity Act 2006 was replaced by Charity Act 2011. Any organization, if it is a charity and is duly registered, must demonstrate that its aims are for the "public good". This requirement is imposed on every organization. A charity does not have goals, some of its activities are aimed at the welfare of society, some are not. The State Charity Commission examines the organization's activities to determine whether the goals of the organization's activities serve the public interest or not. If the Charity Commission considers that social requirements are not met, it will not be registered. The Commission may require a change of purpose before registering an organization to ensure that its purpose or activities meet the "public interest requirements."

The most common historical form is charitable assistance (not a legal entity), sponsors of a charitable organization have the following obligations to perform socially beneficial functions:

- 1) to ensure the implementation of charity goals for the benefit of society;
- 2) To comply with the instructions given by the Charity Commission for socially beneficial purposes;
- 3) to submit full information about their socially beneficial activities to the annual report of the trustees' councils.

A charity fund can use any property without restrictions on its content. At the same time, the sponsors of the charity are required to report to the beneficiaries (not always a fiduciary) about the progress of the charity. Adherence to the "Public Welfare Criteria" - the global obligations of charity sponsors; this is a requirement that is always implemented, not just at the time of registration.

In the US and Canada, non-profit organizations do not need to do this at the state (provincial) level, where necessary, as state (provincial) legislation regulates their status. There are no state independent civil unions in the United States. All associations were established by state or municipal authorities, which played the most important role in this regard. The oldest associations were townships known as "city corporations". The first educational institutions - Harvard (1638) and Yale (1701) were established on the basis of state grants and were managed by priests who were representatives of the church and also under the patronage of the state [6]. The logic of formation of organizational and legal forms of non-governmental non-commercial organizations can be observed by analyzing the history of the US legal system. The first form used for non-commercial purposes was traditionally the trust. The trust was established in the 18th century to manage assets consisting of contributions and donations to city corporations, early educational institutions, and religious organizations. However, American courts intervene in the activities of charitable funds that receive donations. For example, according to the court, in 1993, one of the donations made at Cornell University exceeded the limit established by the state for this educational institution. Common law has defined the requirements for a trust organization used by US courts. The founding documents of a trust must contain three main elements that describe it: the trust, the object and the intention to establish the purpose. The documents constituting the trust define the following: the purposes of the trust; the property entrusted by the founder to the trustee; the names of the beneficiaries or, if the trust is created for charitable purposes, the mechanism by which the beneficiaries can be identified; methods by which trustees manage property for the benefit of certain persons or for certain purposes [7].

CONCLUSION, In addition to bona fide requirements, the requirements of US law of a targeted nature and the inability to establish a clear corporate governance structure have led to the establishment of organizations with effective corporate structure and targeted specialization. The corporation as a general organizational and legal form helped to expand the activities of associations. Creating an internal corporate structure for non-profit organizations has benefited the business community, which defines the most effective governance model for a charitable corporation. It should be noted that the US business community has traditionally been the main source of funding for NGOs. Funds became the next organizational and legal form that ensures the efficiency of management and the closest connection with business. During the rapid development of capitalism, the establishment of funds corresponded to the interests of big capital. In particular, after the death of G. Ford (the founder of the famous Ford company)

in 1947, the voting shares of the companies founded by him were transferred to relatives and the voiceless - the Ford Foundation. Thus, the Ford Foundation was exempted from paying taxes and collected a large amount of money.

Later, in American law, non-profit organizations gained the ability to make a profit, allowing the state to "kill two birds with one stone":

1) financial reporting requirements have been strengthened, as profit-making includes strict and detailed reporting of income and expenses;

2) non-governmental non-profit organizations that provide educational, medical and other socially important services to the population have been equated in the economic situation with commercial organizations that traditionally provide services to the population in the United States.

In the USA, the rapid development of independent non-profit organizations in modern forms begins: 90% of current NGOs were formed after the Second World War [8]. Currently, there are approximately 1.4 million registered charitable organizations in the United States. The most common analysis of US legislation allows determining the following characteristics of a non-profit organization: its purpose - "public interest"; it acts as a "non-harmful" charity; it is based on self-management and self-sufficiency of internal management; subject to compliance with the necessary criteria and conditions, he is exempt from federal taxes, as well as from taxes on property and funds transferred to him.

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